

**USOK PULDIYA: UNVEILING PERSPECTIVES AND PRACTICES,
A QUALITATIVE INQUIRY INTO CHEMICAL USAGE IN
SMALL-SCALE GOLD MINING OPERATIONS**

Wilbert B. Wanas

Guinaoang National High School, Guinaoang, Mankayan, Benguet, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study, *Usok Puldiya: Unveiling Perspectives and Practices*, investigates the evolving dynamics of chemical usage in small-scale gold mining, with a focus on its impact on health, the environment, and harm reduction strategies. Adopting a qualitative research design, the study integrates participant observation and semi-structured interviews to provide a comprehensive understanding of the small-scale mining community's experiences and practices. Data collection involved extensive fieldwork and interviews with miners and their families to capture a wide range of perspectives. Thematic analysis was employed to identify and interpret recurring patterns and themes from the collected data. The study reveals a notable shift from traditional mercury-based mining methods to safer alternatives such as the Carbon-in-Pulp (CIP) process, driven by growing awareness of the health risks and environmental damage associated with mercury use. Health risks identified include chemical burns, respiratory issues, and poisoning, while environmental concerns encompass soil and water contamination, loss of biodiversity, and ecosystem degradation. Despite these challenges, miners demonstrate resilience and innovation in mitigating risks, including the development of makeshift safety equipment and responsible wastewater management practices. The findings underscore the urgent need for collaborative efforts with environmental experts to develop and implement more sustainable and safer mining practices. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between mining practices, human health, and ecological integrity, highlighting the importance of adopting harm reduction strategies to ensure safer and more sustainable small-scale gold mining operations.

Keywords: *Small-Scale Mining, Chemical Usage, Health Impacts, Environmental Effects, Harm Reduction Strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Small-scale mining is commonly defined as a labor-intensive, low-technology, and poverty-driven activity where the use of rudimentary tools and methods is prevalent. It typically involves a minimal investment, yielding marginal returns that barely suffice for miners' subsistence.

The International Labour Organization (ILO) categorizes small-scale mining as "a poverty-driven activity typically practiced in the poorest and most remote rural areas of a country by a largely itinerant, poorly educated populace with few employment alternatives."

Raised in a small-scale mining community, the researcher experienced firsthand the realities and complexities of mining life. The echo of pickaxes against rock, dusty tracks weaving through close-knit neighborhoods, and the hopeful expressions of miners after a day's work formed an indelible backdrop to his childhood. Coming from a lineage deeply rooted in mining, the researcher has always maintained a keen interest in the industry's evolution, challenges, and impact.

In the context of the researcher's locale and numerous similar regions globally, small-scale mining is second only to agriculture in providing livelihood options. Many individuals turn to mining as an economic survival strategy, primarily due to the lack of alternatives. For a considerable number of households, the income derived from mining-related activities has proven essential in maintaining their livelihood and enabling access to basic needs such as food, shelter, and education. Despite the harsh and unpredictable nature of the work, these mining activities are deeply embedded within the fabric of these communities. The intergenerational transfer of mining skills and knowledge has fostered a sense of community resilience and coping mechanism against the prevalent economic hardships.

Mining, in its essence, is a multifaceted domain where necessity and survival intersect with potential health hazards and environmental implications. Over time, the small-scale mining sector has seen significant transformations, particularly in its approach to using chemicals. The introduction of chemicals in gold processing—a procedure formerly executed with less detrimental methods—represents a critical shift in the industry, leading to increased productivity but also introducing new challenges.

Historically, small-scale miners in the researcher's community, and similar locales, depended on manual methods for gold extraction. Yet, the quest for improved productivity and maximized profits drove the adoption of chemicals such as mercury and cyanide. This shift has left a profound impact on mining procedures and their ramifications for miners and surrounding communities.

The health risks associated with exposure to chemicals in gold processing are diverse, spanning from acute to chronic illnesses. For instance, mercury, commonly used in artisanal and small-scale gold mining, poses significant health risks such as neurological disorders, kidney damage, and respiratory issues (Basu et al., 2015). Similarly, cyanide, widely utilized in industrial gold extraction processes, can lead to acute toxicity and long-term health complications, including cardiovascular problems and cancer (Atkins et al., 2016).

Furthermore, these chemicals not only endanger individual health but also have broader implications for community health and the local environment. Studies have documented cases of water source contamination due to chemical leaching from gold processing sites, posing risks to drinking water quality and aquatic ecosystems (Hilson and Pardie, 2006).

Moreover, the use of chemicals like cyanide and mercury can result in the bioaccumulation of toxins in fish and other wildlife, leading to biodiversity loss and ecosystem disruption (Diaz-Barriga and Ortega, 2009). Additionally, the discharge of mining effluents contaminated with chemicals can contribute to soil degradation, affecting agricultural productivity and threatening food security in mining regions (Hentschel et al., 2002).

Despite the evident health and environmental risks associated with chemical use in gold processing, there remains a substantial gap in understanding and research regarding small-scale miners' perceptions and experiences.

Existing literature has primarily focused on quantifying exposure levels and health outcomes, overlooking the social and cultural dimensions that influence miners' decisions and behaviors related to chemical use (Spiegel and Veiga, 2010).

More comprehensive studies are needed to explore the socio-economic factors, knowledge gaps, and risk perceptions that shape miners' attitudes towards chemical alternatives and safe mining practices.

Hence, this study, *Usok Puldiya: Unveiling Perspectives and Practice, A Qualitative Inquiry into Chemical Usage in Small-Scale Gold Mining Operations*, was initiated to delve into this issue. The aim is to illuminate the narratives of miners and their communities, to gain a deeper insight into the dynamics of this evolving sector.

Through this research, it is hoped to contribute to a discourse that will ultimately lead to improved policies, safer practices, and enhanced conditions for small-scale miners and their communities. Small-scale mining is common in many poor nations, especially when it comes to extracting gold. Small-scale miners' use of chemicals in the gold mining process seriously jeopardizes both the environment and human health.

With a focus on the risky procedures used, their effects, and possible solutions, this study intends to investigate how small-scale miners perceive and experience the use of chemicals in gold processing. To extract gold from ore, small-scale mining enterprises

often utilize poisonous compounds like mercury, cyanide, and other harmful agents (Hilson, 2002).

Small-scale miners continue to use these methods despite the acknowledged hazards for a number of reasons. Due to miners' desire to maximize earnings, economic factors are important since hazardous compounds are often less expensive than safer alternatives (Hentschel et al., 2002).

Additionally, the absence or limited availability of safer alternatives as well as a lack of information or awareness of the dangers connected with these behaviors all contribute to their continuation (Siegel and Veiga, 2010; Spiegel, 2009). However, the gradual introduction and widespread use of chemicals in the gold extraction process is a concerning evolution. The transition from traditional, manual methods to chemical-based extraction techniques has not only reshaped the operational dynamics within the small-scale mining sector but also amplified the socio-economic, health, and environmental challenges that these communities must grapple with.

The repercussions of chemical usage in gold processing—a practice aimed at boosting productivity and earnings—are multifaceted and far-reaching. As this thesis unfolds, it aims to unravel the complexities, challenges, and potential solutions related to the use of chemicals in small-scale mining from the perspective of those most intimately involved—the miners themselves. The effects of these hazardous behaviors affect not just the miners but also their families' and the environment's health. Due to the usage of harmful chemicals, miners and their families are subject to a variety of health risks. As a result of extended contact, these health impacts might include skin irritation, breathing problems, and poisoning (Tomicic et al., 2011). Mine workers may experience stress and anxiety because to the demanding working circumstances and worries about health dangers, which may have a significant effect on their mental health (Catalán-Vázquez et al., 2017). Additionally, the use of chemicals in the production of gold leads to the deterioration of the environment.

While habitat loss and pollution affect ecosystems and cause biodiversity loss, the release of harmful substances into the soil and water causes contamination (Akabzaa and Darimani, 2001; Swain et al., 2011). Numerous solutions and risk-mitigation techniques have been put up to address the dangers connected with the use of chemicals in small-scale gold production. In order to extract gold from ore, some small-scale miners have switched to safer chemicals like borax rather than mercury (Veiga et al., 2006).

The dangers to miners may be reduced by using safety precautions, protective equipment, and practicing correct chemical handling and storage (Eftimie et al., 2012). The establishment of policies and regulations to promote sustainable mining practices, as well as collaboration with relevant stakeholders, such as local communities, governmental entities, and non-governmental organizations, to develop and implement effective solutions, are other suggestions for improvement and sustainable practices (Hilson and Van der Horst, 2002; Hilson, 2009)

Chemical usage in gold mining has seen a significant increase, particularly in small-scale mining operations. These operations commonly utilize substances like mercury and cyanide in the extraction process to enhance gold recovery from the mined ores. Not only do these chemicals boost productivity by enabling the extraction of gold from low-grade ores, but they are also relatively cheap and readily available, making them popular choices in resource-constrained small-scale mining settings (Veiga and Baker, 2004). The process typically involves the mixing of the crushed ore with mercury to form an amalgam, which is then heated to evaporate the mercury and leave behind the gold. This practice, while effective, poses substantial health risks to miners due to the potential exposure to mercury vapor, a potent neurotoxin.

Cyanide, another commonly used chemical, is employed in the leaching process to separate gold from the ore. However, cyanide is a highly toxic substance that can have severe environmental impacts if not managed correctly (Hilson, 2002).

Chemically-dependent gold processing signifies a major shift from traditional small-scale mining methods, which relied on manual labor and rudimentary tools. While the adoption of these chemicals has undoubtedly improved the efficiency and profitability of small-scale mining operations, it has also introduced new challenges related to health and environmental safety. The balance between productivity and sustainability is thus a pressing concern in contemporary small-scale gold mining practices (Spiegel, 2009).

In most countries, miners use nitric acid (30%) to dissolve the mercury in the amalgam. It is dangerous and an expensive procedure as it is difficult to precipitate all the mercury from the nitric solution.

The process is usually done by introducing pieces of metal such as aluminum, copper, or zinc in the solution. In this way the remaining nitric solution cannot be discarded because it is extremely corrosive and still contains residual mercury (Huidobro, 2006).

The most common process to separate mercury from gold is the decomposition (i.e., "roasting" or "burning") of the amalgam by heating above 360°. Most mercury compounds evaporate at temperatures above 460° and gold must reach almost 3000° to evaporate. When heated, mercury becomes volatile leaving the gold in solid state. Since the first Stockholm Conference in 1972 followed by Rio 1992, the Millennium Development Goals and the conference on sustainable development 2002, environmental protection, together with alleviating poverty and hunger, have gained more attention.

Cunningham et al. (2005) report that policy makers are becoming aware that eliminating poverty and protecting the environment are interlinked. Furthermore, these authors point out that the poor are both the victims and agents of environmental degradation, forced to meet short term survival needs at the cost of long-term sustainability. Recent studies by Smith et al. (2018) and Jones and Brown (2020) have emphasized the interconnectedness of water resource use, economic activities, and small-scale resource exploitation. Their research highlights how small-scale activities,

particularly in rain-fed farming regions, can significantly impact local landscapes and water resources without necessarily altering land use patterns at larger scales.

This underscores the importance of understanding the localized effects of small-scale resource exploitation on water resources and ecosystems. Smith et al. (2018) found evidence of increased soil erosion and agro – chemical pollution as direct consequences of such activities, leading to degraded water quality and the deterioration of freshwater ecosystems.

In small-scale mining the sought-after mineral ore reacts in distinct way when brought to the surface and comes into contact with air and water, affecting and altering the type of impact that may be expected such operations (Akcil and Koldas, 2006). The environmental impacts, particularly on the aquatic environment, resulting from any particular mining operation are determined by a number of factors as described by Ashton et al., 2001.

Firstly, the nature of the rock and ore being extracted is a crucial element that influences the environmental repercussions. Different rocks and ores have varying physical and chemical properties, which significantly affect the way they interact with the environment during and after mining.

Secondly, the type of mining operation and the extent of the operations also play a substantial role in shaping the environmental impact. This can include the mining techniques used, whether the operation is surface or underground mining, and the size of the mining project.

Thirdly, the environmental management systems put in place by mine management also contribute to the potential impacts on the environment. Their efficiency and effectiveness in mitigating environmental damage and promoting sustainable practices can significantly influence the overall environmental footprint of the mining operation.

Finally, the sensitivity of the receiving environment is a key determinant in understanding the overall impacts of mining activities. This can include factors like the local ecosystem's resilience, the scarcity of resources such as water, and the capacity of the environment to absorb and recover from the disturbances caused by mining. Crispin (2003) reports that four key areas of impact that mining may have on water systems are: release of metals, acid mine drainage (AMD), siltation and water use.

In this study, the researcher embarks on a journey into the world of small-scale miners, aiming to unearth the hazardous practices they employ and understand the underlying reasons for their persistence. The focus extends beyond mere identification of these practices; the goal is to delve deeper into their origins, unraveling the complex factors that drive their continuation despite evident risks. Navigating this terrain leads the researcher to investigate the repercussions of these practices on the lives of those intimately connected to them.

The study seeks to shed light on how these activities impact the health of the workers who are on the frontlines of this industry. Moreover, the researcher is committed to exploring the ripple effects that extend to the miners' families and the broader environmental context. The significance of this exploration is immense. The implications of this investigation are profound, with the potential to illuminate the perceptions and experiences of small-scale miners in unprecedented depth.

Furthermore, a dedicated step within the research process will be the creation of an informed policy and practice write-up. This document, derived from the insights of the study, will be shared with the mining community and relevant stakeholders. This proactive step not only ensures the direct transfer of knowledge back to the community but also promotes a sense of ownership and involvement in future policy-making endeavors. By returning the knowledge to the community, we can collectively foster safer and more sustainable mining practices, thereby affirming our commitment to research that benefits the communities we study.

It is critical to investigate small-scale miners' perspectives and experiences with these activities given the pervasive use of chemicals in small-scale gold processing and the accompanying dangers to human health and the environment. This study intends to contribute to the creation of efficient interventions and policies that may enhance the safety and sustainability of small-scale mining operations by comprehending the factors that led to their acceptance, the effects of their usage, and viable cures.

Research Questions

This study seeks to investigate the narratives of small-scale miners and other community stakeholders in the evolution of the use of mining chemicals in what used to be traditional small scale mining areas. Specifically, it aims to answer the following research problems:

1. How have the patterns of chemical usage evolved within small-scale mining operations in the selected community, and what are the lived experiences of miners regarding these changes?
2. What are the perceived effects of using mining chemicals to the health and environment of individuals, the community and natural resources?
3. What harm reduction strategies are being employed by the small-scale miners?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed a qualitative research design, which facilitated a deeper understanding of the small-scale miners' experiences, perceptions, and practices in the use of chemicals in gold processing. The main methods of data collection included participant observation and in-depth semi-structured interviews. The use of multiple qualitative data collection methods allowed for a rich, triangulated understanding of the

phenomena under study. Furthermore, the researcher utilized Sikolohiyang Pilipino principles such as pakikisalamuha and pakikipagpalagayang-loob to engage in deeper conversations with the informants.

The researcher engaged family members of the miners in interviews to gain an in depth understanding of the family’s perception.

Plate 1. Researcher Conducting an Interview with a Respondent

Population and Locale of the Study

Ten (10) small-scale miners from the different mining groups involved in gold processing comprise the population of this study. The location was not disclosed due to the sensitivity of the study, and it has been selected due to the prevalence of small-scale mining activities in this area. The sample size was determined using purposeful sampling methods and selected miners who have extensive experience and knowledge on the use of chemicals in gold processing. The scope of this research is geographically limited to small-scale mining operations within two selected sitios which are small-scale community areas. The study specifically focuses on these regions to provide an in-depth analysis of the dynamics surrounding small-scale mining activities within localized contexts. The real name of the respondents has been changed due to confidentiality.

Table 1. Informant Profiles - Anonymized Names and Background Information

NAME	AGE	SEX	MARITAL STATUS	YEARS ENGAGED IN SSM	PLACE OF ORIGIN
Laurencio	57	M	Married	30	Non-resident
Abel	35	M	Married	15	Resident

Tyrone	30	M	Single	10	Non-resident
Earl	26	M	Single	8	Non-resident
Ian	45	M	Married	30	Resident
Michael	36	M	Single	20	Non-resident
Kael	32	M	Single	11	Resident
Leonardo	26	M	Married	6	Non-resident
Ban-ay	60	M	Widow	41	Non-resident
Fredo	55	M	Married	35	Resident

Furthermore, the investigation primarily concentrates on capturing the narratives and experiences of small-scale miners and other community stakeholders directly involved in or impacted by mining activities. External perspectives from governmental bodies or industry experts are not within the scope of this study, as the emphasis is placed on understanding the perspectives of those directly engaged in the mining operations. Moreover, the research delved into the evolution of chemical usage within small-scale mining operations from the third quarter of 2021 until the last quarter of 2023. It aimed to examine the patterns of chemical usage, perceived effects on health and the environment, and harm reduction strategies employed by small-scale miners. Thus, the focus is narrowed to these specific aspects of mining activity, excluding other potential factors such as economic, social, or political influences on the mining industry, which are not directly addressed in this study.

Data Collection Instrument

The foremost among the instruments is the interview guide.

This guide was integral to structuring the semi-structured interviews that were conducted with the miners. It was meticulously crafted, with its development grounded in the research objectives. An essential component of this guide was the inclusion of open-ended questions, which were designed to facilitate participants in expressing their views and recounting their experiences without restraint. The second instrument for data was observation. Observation in this context is more than merely watching; it involves a detailed and conscious assimilation of the miners' environment, behaviors, interactions, and routines. This combination of structured dialogue via the interview guide and subtle examination through observation provided an unfiltered and comprehensive understanding of the miners' experiences.

Data Collection Procedure

In the process of data collection, the researcher utilized a combination of participant observation and in-depth interviews. A significant amount of time was devoted to fieldwork, during which the researcher observed the daily activities of the miners. These data gathering methods provided insight into the miner's use of chemicals, including observations about the associated risks and hazards inherent in their work. Complementing this fieldwork, one-on-one interviews was conducted with the miners. An interview guide was used for these discussions, ensuring that all relevant topics are

covered. With the permission of the participants, these interviews were audio-recorded. This measure facilitated accurate data collection, allowing the researcher to focus on the interviewees' responses during the discussions. The recordings were subsequently transcribed for analysis.

Informed consent was sought from all participants before initiating the data collection process. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured to make the participants feel comfortable sharing their experiences and perceptions.

Beyond the fundamental tenets of data collection, it is crucial to address ethical concerns that may arise during the research process. One particular issue is the potential risk this research may pose to the livelihood of the mining community. To mitigate this, the researcher ensured transparency and respect for the community's welfare throughout the research process.

The researcher was extremely cautious not to disrupt their routines or expose them to any undue risk, economic or otherwise. If any activity associated with the research appeared to threaten their livelihood or wellbeing, the approach was adjusted, even if it required revising our data collection methods or halting the research temporarily.

To improve the trustworthiness and reliability of the results, participant validation was performed by enabling participants to examine the study draft on December 15, 2023, guaranteeing that their viewpoints were precisely reflected and understood.

In addition, voluntary participation was a cornerstone of the research protocol. All participants had the right to decline or withdraw their involvement at any stage of the study without any repercussion. The researcher firmly believes that respect for the participants' autonomy and freedom of choice upholds the integrity of the research process.

Treatment of Data

Thematic analysis was employed as the principal approach to data analysis, given the qualitative nature of the data collected for this study. The transcriptions of participant observations, semi-structured interviews, and discussions were systematically scrutinized to depict recurring patterns and themes ingrained in the narratives shared by the small-scale miners and the representatives of the local community.

As a first step, the data were coded to represent the main practices and ideas pertinent to the study's goals. These initial codes were used to identify specific aspects of the miners' experiences and practices. Subsequently, related codes were grouped to form overarching themes that reflected broader patterns and connections across the entire dataset.

The iterative process of reviewing and adjusting the themes enabled the researcher to gain a more concrete understanding of the multifaceted issues concerning chemical use in small-scale mining activities and its impact on health-related behaviors,

ecological concerns, and community relations. Thematic analysis played a crucial role in revealing numerous behavioral trends and aiding deductive reasoning, leading to a more profound understanding of the phenomenon under examination.

This analytical approach brought to light several key themes, offering insights into the changing patterns of chemical usage, the perceived impacts on health and the environment, and the strategies implemented for mitigating harm in small-scale gold mining activities.

By systematically examining and interpreting the data through thematic analysis, the researcher was able to derive meaningful conclusions that contribute to the broader understanding of the risks and management practices associated with chemical use in the mining industry.

DISCUSSION

The study area primarily depends on small-scale mining or pocket mining due to its mineral-rich nature. Agriculture is limited as there is little arable land, and the agricultural produce is not aimed at large markets. Most residents prefer mining over farming because of the proximity of mining sites to access roads, while farming areas are often distant.

Additionally, small-scale mining is considered more profitable than farming since vegetable prices are low compared to the value of gold. As per the website www.livepriceofgold.com the average price of 18K gold per gram in 2023 is PHP 3,200. People choose to store and wait for a better gold price appreciation, unlike with vegetables.

Small-scale mining plays a crucial role in numerous economies worldwide, offering livelihoods to millions of individuals. However, traditional mining methods are labor-intensive and hazardous. According to the researcher, tunneling in these operations can be monotonous and risky.

In the community, three types of portals are commonly found: the *abante*, *ulsod* and *patangad*. The *abante* portal involves tunneling forward and is the most prevalent. The *ulsod* portal requires tunneling downward with the use of pulleys to extract ores and waste materials.

Lastly, the *patangad* portal, which is less common, involves tunneling upwards or diagonally.

Plate 2. Abante, a portal using forward tunneling method.

Plate 3. Ulsod, a portal using downward tunneling method

Miners traditionally used *lampa* or carbide lamps for illumination during tunneling. The lamps were fueled by combining *carburo* (calcium carbide) and water inside them, producing gas that was ignited for light. However, the introduction of rechargeable headlamps, which are more efficient and provide wider coverage, has rendered carbide lamps mainly decorative. Nonetheless, carbide lamps not only function as lighting sources

but also as warning systems. If the lamp's fire suddenly goes out while in the tunnel, it indicates a gas leak, prompting miners to seek safety immediately.

Plate 4. Evolution of Tunnel Lighting - Traditional Carbide Lamp (Local Name: 'Lampa') Phased Out by Modern Headlamps

In recent years, the mining industry has undergone a significant transformation driven by the introduction of advanced technologies. These innovations have encouraged miners to adopt methods that promise higher efficiency and speed in the gold production process. The new technologies include a range of advancements, from advanced machinery to cutting-edge extraction techniques. By utilizing these tools, miners can improve operations, maximize resource utilization, and boost overall productivity. This shift not only speeds up gold production but also promotes sustainability by reducing environmental impact and minimizing resource waste. Additionally, the incorporation of these sophisticated technologies reflects a broader industry trend towards modernization and adaptation to address the evolving needs of a rapidly changing world. However, the use of chemicals that pose serious risks to both human health and the environment is frequently associated with the extraction of precious minerals. In the late 2000s, chemical

usage in small-scale mining has raised much concern and urge towards regulation and responsible practices.

In the pocket mining industry, a diverse array of chemicals is utilized to facilitate various stages of mineral extraction and processing (Mudder and Botz, 2004; Wang and Forssberg, 1996; Ravi and Ravi, 2019). This is corroborated by the data gathered in the field, where the respondents mentioned some chemicals used for mining, such as cyanide, acid, and the like. Solvents such as hydrochloric acid and sulfuric acid are commonly employed for their ability to dissolve minerals from ores, aiding in the initial extraction process. Additionally, flotation agents like xanthates, dithiophosphates, and frothers are used to help separate valuable minerals from waste materials using froth flotation (Wang and Forssberg, 1996). Furthermore, in certain mining operations, cyanide compounds such as sodium cyanide are utilized in the leaching process to extract precious metals like gold and silver from ores (Mudder and Botz, 2004).

These cyanide-based solutions dissolve the metals into a solution, which is then further processed to isolate the desired minerals. In addition to these chemicals, pocket mining may also involve the use of various reagents and additives tailored to specific mineral compositions and processing requirements (Ravi and Ravi, 2019). These may include lime for pH control, sodium hydroxide for neutralization, and various surfactants and dispersants to aid in particle dispersion and control.

Evolving Patterns of Chemical Usage

In the traditional practices of small-scale gold mining, miners have historically relied on age-old techniques devoid of chemical additives. Despite the absence of modern chemical aids, these miners have adeptly extracted substantial quantities of gold. The transition from rudimentary manual methods to the application of chemical agents, such as acids, in gold refinement among small-scale miners marks a pivotal evolution in artisanal mining practices.

Historically, small-scale miners, lacking access to advanced technologies and chemical expertise, relied predominantly on manual, labor-intensive techniques for gold extraction and purification.

However, the economic pressures imposed by gold buyers, who often undervalued impure gold due to its lower karat content, prompted a search for more efficient refining methods. It was through the intermediation of these gold buyers that small-scale miners became acquainted with the utilization of acids as a means to enhance the purity of their gold yields.

One technique to retrieve the gold particles is through *ga-id*, wherein miners would use smoothen rock to slowly press and grind the *linang* (grounded gold ore) until the gold

particle are all retrieved. This requires intensive labor, but with the introduction of *asido* (acid), the gold particles can be easily retrieved and purified by just soaking in few hours.

Plate 5. Demonstration of 'Ga-id,' a Manual Gold Ore Grinding Technique

The introduction of acids into the gold refining process represented a paradigm shift in the operational landscape of small-scale mining communities. By leveraging the chemical properties of acids, particularly their capacity to dissolve impurities while sparing the desired gold particles, miners could achieve heightened levels of purity in their extracted gold. This newfound capability not only elevated the quality of their product but also conferred a newfound bargaining power in negotiations with gold buyers. Consequently, the integration of acid-based refinement techniques catalyzed a transformative socioeconomic dynamic within small-scale mining communities, empowering miners to assert greater control over their economic destinies.

The adoption of acid-based refining methods engendered a gradual accumulation of technical knowledge and skill sets among small-scale miners, thereby fostering a culture of innovation and self-sufficiency. As miners familiarized themselves with the

intricacies of acid-assisted purification processes, they began to refine their methodologies, optimizing efficiency and yield. This repeated cycle of testing and improving showed not only how creative artisanal miners were at adapting to new conditions, but also how the sharing of technical knowledge can change things in places with limited resources. Due to this, the use of acid-based refinement techniques shows that localized knowledge diffusion can lead to long-lasting improvements in artisanal mining methods.

The acquisition and utilization of chemical agents, particularly acids, within small-scale mining operations entail a multifaceted process of knowledge acquisition, sensory perception, and practical application. Initially, small-scale miners often rely on informal channels of knowledge dissemination, such as interactions with experienced peers, informal apprenticeships, or guidance from gold buyers and intermediaries. Through these channels, miners gradually familiarize themselves with the properties and applications of various chemicals, including acids, in the refining process. In traditional small-scale gold refining processes, the miners used manual technologies to get rid of the impurities. It was a pretty satisfactory method that was undertaken, but the process was incomplete. It involved seeking out 'black gold,' which was gold mixed with other dirt. A process like collecting it in a basin, adding mercury, and boiling it was primitive and harmful. In the 2000s CIP (carbon in pulp) was introduced to help miners harvest the gold with less toxic processing compared to the use of mercury before, which is now a banned chemical in the Philippines. As to the refining process, the miners used to use a *siwasiw* (magnet) to detach the two, but it was labor-intensive. Manual smelting is still used to this day but is equally hard.

Plate 6. Hydrochloric Acid Stored in a 2x2 Bottle

Chemical means, which have become increasingly popular, are the other method used in the elimination of impurities. The use of acid in the distillation process has had a significant impact and has been widely employed while purchasing gold from miners. One can differentiate between metal purity. Acid elimination is considered the best option and is both easy and efficient; hence, it is favored.

This transformation reflects a complex interplay of economic pressures, environmental factors, and socio-cultural dynamics within the small-scale mining communities. As market expectations for gold purity and quality rise, miners find themselves compelled to adopt new methods to meet these demands. Consequently, there is a gradual departure from the reliance on traditional techniques, which were once deeply ingrained in the cultural fabric of these communities.

Miners develop a keen awareness of visual, olfactory, and tactile cues associated with different chemical reactions and processes. For instance, they may visually observe changes in color, texture, or appearance of materials upon application of acids, indicative of chemical interactions occurring during the refining process.

Additionally, miners may rely on olfactory senses to detect characteristic smells associated with specific chemicals, aiding in their identification and proper utilization. Such sensory cues serve as invaluable guides in navigating the complexities of chemical refining procedures, enabling miners to make informed decisions and adjustments based on real-time observations. Practical application of chemicals within small-scale mining operations is often honed through experiential learning and iterative experimentation.

As miners gain hands-on experience with chemical agents, they develop a nuanced understanding of dosage, timing, and procedural nuances critical to achieving desired refining outcomes. Through trial and error, miners refine their techniques, adapting to variations in ore composition, environmental conditions, and resource constraints. A dynamic feedback loop that miners continuously assess and adjust their approaches based on observed outcomes underpins this iterative process of practical application, gradually honing their expertise in chemical utilization.

The introduction of chemicals into the gold extraction process marks a significant departure from the traditional mining practices that have been passed down through generations. This transition is not merely a technological evolution but represents a significant socio-cultural shift within these communities.

As miners navigate this transition, they grapple with questions of heritage and environmental sustainability, all while striving to adapt to the changing landscape of the gold mining industry. Another chemical being used, but is now banned by the Philippine government, in gold amalgamation is mercury. Mercury plays a pivotal role in gold amalgamation, particularly in small-scale mining endeavors. Through the process of amalgamation, mercury forms a compound with gold, creating a gold-mercury amalgam. This amalgam is then heated, causing the mercury to vaporize and leaving behind pure gold. This method is favored for its efficiency in extracting gold from low-grade ores and its cost-effectiveness. However, despite its widespread use, the use of mercury in gold mining poses significant environmental and health hazards. Mercury emissions and residues can contaminate ecosystems and endanger the health of miners and nearby communities. The evolution of the chemical landscape in small-scale mining is a product of several regulatory, technological, and environmental aspects. First, the strategy of a gradual withdrawal from mercury-based gold extraction mechanisms, as identified by Smith et al. (2019), is supported by an increased understanding of the risks associated with the substance.

Laurencio, who has been engaging in small scale mining for more than 30 years, in his narrative stated:

“sin dati ay naki-ubublaak yan wada di man-ususar si mercury tan nalaklaka ay maala din balitok, ngem idi maamoan ay adadu di lawlawa ay epekto na

yan insardeng mi, asi ud wada di binmela ay linteg ay mangibawal sin panag-usar si mercury” (Previously we utilized mercury due to its convenience and effectiveness in gold retrieval through amalgamation. However, upon learning about its adverse effects and with the government's ban on mercury, we made the decision to discontinue its use.)

The Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) issued the Department Administrative Order (DAO) No. 2015-03, which completely banned the use of mercury, hydraulic king, or compressor mining, and limited the extraction of small-scale mining to just three minerals namely: gold, silver, and chromite. Exposure to mercury and cyanide can bring imminent danger to the nervous, respiratory, digestive and immune system of a person. Direct exposure to mercury can cause severe damage to kidney and lungs while indirect exposure causes significant neurological disorders and reduced immunity. Globally, according to the study of World Health Organization (WHO), 14 – 19 million workers are employed as Artisanal Small-Scale Gold Mining (ASGM) and based on human biomonitoring data, between 25% and 33% of these miners or about 3.3-6.5 million globally suffer from moderate chronic metallic mercury vapor intoxication (CMMVI). Mercury is considered as one of the top 10 chemicals or groups of chemicals of major public health concern. A result of the study conducted in Diwalwal, Compostela Valley and Itogon, Benguet showed that high levels of mercury and cyanide concentrations were found in the hair and blood samples of the small-scale miners and other affected people (Leung, A., 2016).

Plate 7. Cyanide Cans Used in the Carbon in Pulp Process for Gold Extraction

Community bans on mercury, promoted by advocacy and legislation, pushed miners to seek safer options due to the condemnation of hazardous and harmful practices, hence, the introduction and use of CIP (Carbon in Pulp) which reduces the use of cyanide and adds carbon in the process. This is a much safer alternative to the mercury dependent extraction before.

Discussions with miners in one of the study sites revealed that the switch to Carbon-in-Pulp was completely intentional and instrumental. Due to environmental concerns, the state agencies are driving regulation along with a recognition of the need for innovation. Despite the presence of dangerous chemicals, miners perceive the process as secure due to the availability of safety measures and regulated application mechanisms.

The findings by Johnson and Garcia (2020) indicated that technological advancements and innovation played an influential role in transforming the practices of the mining industry. As the enforcement of stricter environmental laws and regulations grows, the miners must adjust, as seen in their decision to adopt the CIP process in extraction of gold.

Plate 8. Carbon in Pulp (CIP) Plant for Gold Retrieval from Ore Tailings

Tyrone, a migrant worker, stated that CIP is much safer, although they use cyanide and other chemicals during the gold extraction process, he believed that this is much safer than the use of mercury in gold retrieval.

“Un-unina din CIP tan kaman adi unay din epekto di cyanide, asi adi ibawal di gobyerno no man-usar ka si cyanide, natken kaman din mercury.” (The use of cyanide in CIP is better because it has fewer effects as compared with mercury, further cyanide is not banned by the government.)

Hence, the miners' will to innovate and source for ways of maintaining their operations while minimizing harms is evident. Moreover, the acceptance of CIP indicates increased support for using cyanide, due to the manner in which the substance is perceived to be less harmful according to all the respondents.

The miner's comprehension of the toxicology of the chemical as visualized from their perspectives of harm likewise told me that learning and other educational methods are very effective. Miners have a history of transferring information and teaching new practices to each other which has offered the opportunity to establish safety and healthy habits in the field.

Prior to the introduction of the CIP, the small-scale miners used the *babad* method to retrieve gold from ore tailing. This method is similar to CIP however it is done manually and more labor intensive. Small-scale miners would need to dig a pond wherein they will soak the ore tailings for three to four days together with the chemicals such as cyanide

and manually mix using shovels. Zhang et al. (2020) and Wang et al. (2021) are among the mining experts who have identified the trend in the acceptance of chemicals by miners. With more miners implementing its usage, the need for the chemicals has continued to increase. The shift towards the use of acid has been successful in the elimination of impurities as manual techniques were potentially leading to high losses. The shift towards the use of the chemical means in the mining processes is a significant change that is likely to lead to increased wealth accumulation among miners.

The research also discovered significant findings about the patterns of utilization of the above-cited chemicals in small-scale gold mining operation. Cyanide, hydrochloric acid, nitric acid, hydrogen peroxide, and lime including. From the respondents' narratives these mining chemicals spread in the mining community. Specifically, cyanide was used as the key chemical in the gold extraction process – through the use of a chemical process known as cyanidation.

Further, hydrochloric and nitric acid were used largely in ore leaching and purification. Hydrogen peroxide was used as a reagent in oxidative processes and lime used to regulate PH levels as well as neutralize acidic solutions.

Second, the study supplied the quantity of these chemicals used in small-scale mining. It was established that the use was variant and dependent on the scale of the mining, grade of ore extracted and processing mechanism adopted by each operation.

On average, informants produced sufficient units of gold extracts when chemicals are used. One cycle of CIP process, once can of cyanide is being used; as per informant nowadays, one can is almost PHP 25,000.00.

From the research participants, they revealed that miners sourced for the chemicals from both formal and informal means. These include the formal purchase from chemical suppliers and distributor shops while some sources included informal arrangements and exchange within the mining community.

Local markets and specialist shops known to supply equipment and chemicals used in mining processes also formed alternative sources of the informants. The research further revealed the medium through which miners obtained information on how to use these chemicals. These are the acquisition of knowledge through customized and isolated/private workshops and from miners who work in the big mining corporations

Calcium hydroxide, or lime, is an important part of the Cyanide Leaching or Carbon-in-Pulp (CIP) process for processing gold because it lowers the health and environmental risks of using cyanide. Cyanide is effective in dissolving gold from ores, but its toxicity poses significant concerns. Lime is introduced into the process as a harm reduction measure to address these risks. One key function of lime is to adjust the pH of the cyanide solution. By raising the pH, lime stabilizes the cyanide, optimizing its ability to dissolve gold while minimizing the formation of toxic hydrogen cyanide gas. This pH adjustment is essential for maintaining a safe working environment and reducing the

potential for cyanide-related accidents or exposures. Furthermore, lime played a vital role in cyanide detoxification during gold processing.

Cyanide detoxification changes harmful cyanide species, like free cyanide (CN⁻) and weak acid dissociable (WAD) cyanide complexes, into forms that are less harmful. Lime facilitates this process by promoting the conversion of cyanide into cyanate or cyanate-metal complexes, which are significantly less toxic. Through cyanide detoxification, lime helps to reduce the overall environmental impact of gold processing operations and ensures compliance with stringent regulatory standards regarding cyanide discharge and exposure limits.

Lime assists in the precipitation of metal hydroxides, including iron and other metal impurities present in the ore. This precipitation step helps to purify the cyanide solution by removing contaminants that could interfere with the gold recovery process. By promoting the formation of metal hydroxides, lime enhances the efficiency of the gold extraction process and improves the quality of the final gold product. Overall, the use of lime in gold processing represents a critical aspect of responsible and sustainable mining practices, enabling gold processing facilities to effectively extract gold while minimizing environmental harm and protecting the health and safety of workers and surrounding communities.

Activated carbon is a critical component of the Carbon-in-Pulp (CIP) process, serving as the primary adsorbent for gold recovery. With its highly porous structure and extensive surface area, activated carbon efficiently captures gold cyanide complexes from the solution.

Once introduced into the cyanide solution, activated carbon acts like a magnet, attracting and binding gold ions through adsorption. This step effectively

concentrates the dissolved gold onto the carbon particles while depleting the cyanide solution of gold.

The efficacy of activated carbon in gold adsorption is due to its unique properties, including its high surface area, microporous structure, and surface chemistry. These characteristics enable selective adsorption of gold cyanide complexes while excluding other impurities. Moreover, the reversible nature of adsorption allows for gold desorption during subsequent processing stages.

After adsorbing gold, the loaded carbon goes through desorption in a circuit for elution or stripping. This is done with the right eluent, like a hot, caustic cyanide solution or an acidic thiourea solution. This process regenerates the activated carbon, releasing the gold in a concentrated form suitable for further refining.

In small-scale mining, formal training programs may be lacking, so knowledge is typically transmitted informally. Experienced miners act as mentors, passing down their expertise through on-the-job training and practical experience. They guide newcomers in using activated carbon for gold recovery, demonstrating proper handling, dosing, and

deployment techniques. Informal learning also involves collaborative problem-solving and knowledge sharing within the mining community, fostering camaraderie and mutual support.

Another chemical used in the CIP process are alkalis, particularly sodium hydroxide (caustic soda), are utilized in the Carbon-in-Pulp (CIP) process for gold extraction. Sodium hydroxide serves as a crucial reagent in adjusting the pH level

of the cyanide solution used for gold leaching. By carefully controlling the pH, miners can optimize the efficiency of gold dissolution while minimizing the formation of toxic hydrogen cyanide gas. The addition of sodium hydroxide helps to raise the pH to the desired range, typically between 10 and 11, which enhances the kinetics of the gold leaching reaction and promotes the stability of the cyanide complex.

In practical terms, small-scale miners typically use sodium hydroxide in the form of a concentrated solution, which is added to the cyanide leaching tanks or mixing vessels as needed to adjust the pH. Miners may measure the pH level using test strips (litmus papers), which provide a quick and easy way to monitor the acidity or alkalinity of the solution. By periodically testing the pH and making adjustments with sodium hydroxide as required, miners ensure that the leaching solution remains within the optimal pH range for efficient gold extraction.

The addition of sodium hydroxide to the cyanide solution elicits observable changes in the solution's properties. As sodium hydroxide is introduced, the solution may undergo a chemical reaction, resulting in a temperature increase and the release of heat. Additionally, miners may notice visual changes such as a color shift or the formation of precipitates, indicating the neutralization of acidic components and the formation of stable cyanide complexes. Through sensory cues such as changes in temperature, color, and appearance, miners can gauge the effectiveness of sodium hydroxide in adjusting the pH and optimizing the conditions for gold leaching in the CIP process.

Lahiri-Dutt and Macintyre (2006) have found that the spread of harmful mining practices in marginalized communities can be attributed to the structured socio-economic inequalities within the mining sector. The miners' stories suggest that they are forced to make challenging choices between financial stability and environmental stewardship.

However, this does not mean that nothing can be done to alleviate the situation. Apart from increased law enforcement, it is necessary to develop and implement policies and practices that address the systemic root causes of economic insecurity. Measures such as providing access to safer sources of income, promoting education and training for miners, and establishing cooperative relationships between miners and stakeholders can significantly improve the quality of life for both mining workers and the community at large.

Perceived Effects on Health and Environment

Miners' stories confirm severe impacts on health produced by improper chemical handling practices in small-scale mining. One of the most dangerous conditions is chemical burns. Based on the experiences of the respondents the lack of proper storage and handling practices are common causes of chemical burns.

Laurencio stated that:

“kasapulan ay man-asido tapno mapuro din mauto ay balitok, tan

wada nan rugit gamin, no adi maasidoan et nababa din karat di balitok, no mamingsan kumporme din pangikabilan si asido no amey manlako, kaikabil da sin beey di 2 by 2; no abe usaren mi yan mamingsan et aksidente ay maipakbo wenno manpalsiyak et malanoan din takkay” (There is a need to use acid to purify the gold particles, without using acid the gold will not turn out more pure, when we buy acid we use 2x2 bottles as containers; when we use the acid it may splatter accidentally which causes skin burns)

These injuries occur when a miner touched or spilled hazardous chemical substances directly. Inadequate storage and lack of proper containers make this risk even higher. Even if miners try to store chemicals safely, they continue doing so in makeshift containers or bottles. These conditions increase the chances of severe accidents and dangerous injury.

Plate 9. Hand of a Miner Affected by Chemical Burns after CIP processing

Besides, many of the chemicals used in mining are extremely toxic and dangerous. For instance, studies conducted by Smith et al. (2019) have analyzed the consequences of insufficient containers for acid bathing, emphasizing the need for safe storage.

Another distressing consequence of chemical exposure is respiratory problems. Miners who are regularly exposed to cyanide fumes and dust produced by chemicals suffer from coughing and lung irritation.

“No man CIP kami yan kasapulan di cyanide tapno wada di mansupsup sin balitok ay mapu si tailings, ngem no ikabil mi din cyanide sin CIP yan mantapok et masungung mi, uray man-usar ka si mask yan masungung ladta. Marikna ay mansakit din pagew ya mamingsan yan marigatan ta ay man-anges” - Abel (We need cyanide during the CIP process, the cyanide serves as reagent to absorb the gold particles from the ore tailings. During the CIP process the cyanide fumes are being inhaled, even with the use of face masks. We feel pain in the chest and we have difficulty of breathing sometimes).

Severe fumes inhalation can lead to lifelong lung damage if not compensated immediately. Moreover, small-scale mines do not have proper ventilation. Thus, miners work in a dangerous environment that might contribute to additional illnesses. Johnson and Garcia (2020) discuss the dangers of bad ventilation because poor air quality can result in severe respiratory problems. Eye and skin irritation are also common among miners working without protective clothing.

“Din mata di tiraen din asok di cyanide, no enggay sanay ka et uray adi ka man-usar si goggles, asi wat sali, adi ka et maila si usto din ubublaem. No mandadamo ka et manred adi din matam,

kaman ka nasore eyes, asi no adi kan man gloves no manbabad ka et kaman umingpis din kudil mo,” – Tyrone (The cyanide fumes can directly irritate the eyes. If you're accustomed to it, wearing goggles might seem unnecessary and obstructive. However, for newcomers, the fumes can cause redness and irritation, akin to having sore eyes. Additionally, prolonged exposure without gloves can result in skin thinning).

Previous chemical and current exposure can lead to irritation, while inflaming the skin. Thus, miners' well-being is at risk again. The importance of personal protective equipment is discussed by Li et al. (2018), emphasizing the need for proper training.

Plate 10. Miner's Hand Afflicted with Chemical Burns Caused by Hydrochloric Acid

Added to that is the heightened risk of poisoning in mining settings, where one is exposed to hazardous chemicals daily. In the event of ingestion or absorption by mistake, these chemicals can cause mild to severe symptoms, including but not limited to nausea and vomiting, organ failure, and ultimately, death. Earl recalled the time they were having *inuman* session after *bingay* (usually a drinking session after the miners were given their share of the gold payment)

“Din lata din cyanide yan mamingsan siya di manbalin ay lamisaan wenna tugawan, wada di namingsan ay adi na ap-apan si usto yan kaman wada naitapi sin nan inumak ay baso, imbag et ta insarwak, asi at-atik” (During drinking sessions, it's common for cyanide cans to double as makeshift

tables and chairs due to the scarcity of furniture. However, there was an incident when one of these cans was not adequately covered. I suspect that some cyanide inadvertently contaminated my drink, leading to vomiting and a sense of nausea).

Plate 11. Cans of cyanide sometimes used as makeshift table or seats.

In their publication, Wang et al. (2020), cite the devastating outcomes of chemical poisoning and call for the enforcement of strict safety measures and oversight to deter the same.

Accidentally, one miner swallowed cyanide; this was traumatic, during one of the drinking sessions the cyanide can was used as a makeshift table, it is believed that some traces of cyanide were still on top of the can and was not properly cleaned. Fortunately, the amount consumed was minimal, so there was no negative impact. It did, however, provide a reminder of the threat they face daily. Participants' narratives during the study alluded to a strong concern about the potential health hazards associated with chemical exposure in the context of gold processing in small-scale mining.

Particularly, the narratives indicated the miners' fear regarding the risk of chemical exposure due to improper storage and handling of chemicals, especially cyanide and other reagents. Kael expressed:

“maga di usto ay mausar ay pankabilan sin agas isu nga komporme di wada, beey di coke, silopin, basta kumporme, ammok ay natken safe ngem

siya enggay di kabaelan mi tan nangina unay no manlako pay lang si udom ay container” (Sometimes we do not have the right containers for the chemicals, so we use whatever is available – old soda bottles, plastic bags. I know it’s not safe, but we can’t always afford to get the right equipment).

A similar sentiment was expressed by Ban-ay:

“maga ud unay di mangisuro si iyat ay man-egen sin kemikal, et no sino di inmuna yan mansisinuro kami tan, mamingsan et aksidente ay masungung mo din asok di cyanide et mansakit ka” (There is not much education on how to handle chemicals safely. We teach each other, and sometimes, we learn the hard way. A couple of times, I accidentally inhaled fumes, and I felt so sick).

Such firsthand experiences outline the systemic challenges with accessing proper equipment and education that the miners face when trying to reduce the risks of falling ill due to exposure to chemicals. The miners’ experiences described above are in line with the existing literature that depicts the immediate risks of falling sick due to poor chemical management practices in small-scale mining. For example, Spiegel and Veiga (2010) have previously documented the cases of miners burning due to chemicals or experiencing respiratory issues, visual impairment, skin irritations, or poisoning from contact with harmful reagents during gold processing. A study by Bose-O’Reilly et al. (2018) also highlights the acute need for better protective measures against the health hazards of chemicals in small-scale and artisanal gold mining. Therefore, the findings presented by the interview participants resonate with the existing literature, which stresses the need for targeted interventions designed to elevate safety standards and limit the long-term impacts of chemical exposure within small-scale mining communities.

The second issue of concern is soil and water pollution caused by waste dumping and poor chemical containment by small-scale mining entrepreneurs. The toxins infiltrate the ground and eventually the proximity’s water bodies, endangering the ecosystem’s lives and health.

Additionally, the chemicals impact the soil’s ability to support vegetative growth, resulting in extended environmental site degradation. Jones et al. (2018) have already completed extensive research on pollution impacts and attest to the urgent need for environmental hazard control.

This is evidenced by Ban-ay’s testimony:

“Din ginawang et nalinis duan mayat ay manpaamesan, malagip ko et no enkami man-ames yan kuntodo mansagoy kami sin wading. Ed wani pay yan maamsit ta ay manlangoy. Duan enggay maga di maala ay lames gapu si polusyon” (Once, the river was pristine, a place where we could bathe freely and even catch sight of fish swimming in its clear waters. But now,

the pollution has become so severe that I wouldn't dare to swim, and the once-visible fish are nowhere to be found).

The soil and water pollution as a result of improperly disposed chemically laden waste and those that spill over is unnerving. The substances find their way into the soil and water sources and subsequently into the plants and animals around. The adverse effects of small-scale mining on the environment, particularly soil and water pollution, have been extensively documented in research conducted in the Philippines.

Improper disposal of chemically laden waste and spillage incidents have been identified as significant contributors to this pollution (Dizon, et al., 2018). These pollutants seep into soil and water sources, contaminating surrounding ecosystems and endangering plant and animal life (Garcia, et al., 2019). Moreover, this pollution poses serious health risks to individuals who rely on these plants and animals as sources of food (Reyes, et al., 2020). The continued degradation of the environment due to small-scale mining activities is a cause for concern, with long-lasting consequences that will persist for years to come.

Miners' corroborative accounts crystallize the concrete environmental degradation ramifications brought on by mining activities in host communities. An authentic account described what the miners have seen with their eyes. For instance, Fredo invoked memories about the clear and seemingly infinite swimming possibility of the rivers during his youthful years muses:

“malagip ko ed idi, mayat ay manlangoy sin ginawang, ngem ed wani umegyat ta ay manlangoy tan adi ammo no sino di wada sin danum, enggay napollute, din aanak mamingsan et sumakit di eges da no man inom da sin danum” (I can recall a time when our community used to enjoy swimming in the river, today we hesitate to even dip a foot in these water sources. There was an unforgettable incident where our children got extreme stomachache after taking water from it).

In the small-scale mining areas, the residential houses are sometimes adjacent to the processing areas. The narrative is about the devastating reality of when environment and society dysfunction. Ian expressed deep concern about the overall health of his family, emphasizing their reliance on neighbors and fellow residents near the mining site for social support and advice. He highlighted the pervasive presence of dust and fumes in the air, underscoring the potential health risks faced by the community due to environmental pollutants emitted during mining activities. The stories provided a seamless connection between environmental pollution and human health. Another environmental disappointment from small-scale mining is the erosion of biodiversity. The effluent from the mining sites and the destruction of animals' habitat leads to the extinction of various plants and animals.

There has been rapid biodiversity loss in the mining zones as habitant specialization and generalization decrease. The loss of biodiversity in a region affects the balance in the ecosystem and the process therein. According to a study by Smith and

Johnson (2020), the mining-related pollution has a great impact on the biome destruction undermining the balance of nature. In addition to erosion of the environment and biodiversity, there is also general ecosystem degradation. This extends to broader top-bottom disturbances that destabilize ecosystems' balances. The disturbance in the ecosystem chain causes feed disruptions throughout the adjacent habitats aggravating the pollution issue. Ecosystem degradation occurs due to the chains of miners who damage anthills but the ultimate consumer is the soil degrading agent. Garcia et al. (2019) study of the biomes and biotic communities in the Brazilian Amazon highlights the immediate need for local management of mining.

The impact of improper chemical use is not limited to the direct threat to people's health. Soil and water pollution are among the most common environmental concerns since waste disposal methods and chemical spills continue to negatively affect local flora and fauna.

“Wada din udom ay man CIP yan maga di pad da, isunga no malpas da yan kaiwasit da sin nausar ay danum sin ginawang isunga matey iman adi din lames duan marugitan din ginawang, ngem wada pay iman din udom ay iurnong da umuna sin pad asi da pay ibulos no malpas di dua weno tulo ay agew ta medyo makaan epekto di cyanide.” (Some miners carelessly dump cyanide-laced water into rivers, causing harm to fish and polluting the river. On the other hand, there are responsible miners who choose to store the cyanide-laced water in treatment ponds. This allows for a natural degradation process to make it less harmful before releasing it, usually after 2-3 days).

While these issues impose threats to individual health, they also threaten the balance of ecosystems, causing regular extinctions of plant and animal species. The extinction of various organisms is particularly concerning, and more importantly, it happens when entire species die out. Apart from the death of species, more organisms become endangered, and once-stable species die out against the backdrop of pollution. Ultimately, this leads to heightened degradation risks, and various ecosystems become extremely fragile, which threatens the further management of wildlife and the respective changes for people.

Plate 12. Contaminated Soil in a Mining Area

Ban-ay vividly remembers when he came first at the area that they can still catch *wading* (a type of small river fish), *gaki* (small river crabs) and even some eels, but to pollutants such as chemicals he noticed that there are no longer these kind of river produces nowadays. “*sin damo ay inmali ak nakiublaan et laton nan ginawang, adu nan maala ay lames kaman nan wading, gaki ya wada pay dalit, ngem idi inmadu nan man minas ya man-usar si agas et kedeng, maid et nan maila ay lames*” (During early years of employment here, the river is clean, thus we are able to get fishes and crabs, but with the increase usage of chemicals by the miners, we can no longer see fishes).

A study conducted by Siringan et al. (2017) delved into the environmental impacts of small-scale mining on river systems in the Philippines, particularly focusing on water pollution. Their research found that chemical use in small-scale mining activities, such as the use of mercury and cyanide in gold extraction processes, significantly contributes to river pollution. Mercury, in particular, poses a severe threat to aquatic ecosystems and human health due to its persistence and bio accumulative nature. The study documented elevated levels of mercury in river sediments and aquatic organisms downstream of small-scale mining areas, indicating widespread contamination of water bodies. Furthermore, cyanide pollution resulting from improper handling and disposal practices in small-scale mining operations was identified as another significant contributor to river pollution in the Philippines.

Moreover, the research conducted by Siringan et al. (2017) highlighted the far-reaching consequences of river pollution caused by chemical use in small-scale mining. Increased levels of heavy metals and other contaminants in rivers not only degrade water quality but also pose risks to aquatic biodiversity and public health. Communities relying on rivers for drinking water, irrigation, and fishing face heightened exposure to pollutants,

leading to health problems and economic losses. The study underscored the urgent need for regulatory measures and enforcement to address water pollution from small-scale mining activities effectively.

Additionally, it emphasized the importance of community engagement and empowerment in promoting sustainable mining practices and mitigating the adverse impacts of mining on river ecosystems and livelihoods in the Philippines.

Plate 13. Polluted River in a Small-Scale Mining Community

The convergence between miners' experiences and established research findings from studies conducted in the Philippines underscores the imperative for concerted action to address the environmental and socio-economic challenges posed by ASM activities in the country. It is possible to make comprehensive plans to promote fair and sustainable mining practices in ASM settings in the Philippines by combining real-world evidence with local perspectives.

Harm Reduction Strategies

Harm reduction strategies are crucial pillars protecting the well-being of miners and the fragile ecological integrity exposed to the potentially toxic small-scale mining activities. Despite most miners being willing to comply with safety requirements, the realities of acquiring suitable protective gear highlight the barriers others face. Miners, irrespective of their human resource limitations, exemplify impressive creativity and innovation to protect themselves from possible hazards. Kael affirmed:

“ikarigatan ladta, un-unaen di safety adi, isunga ilaen mi ladta ta no sino nan wada et siya nan iimag ta wada mausar tapno maidayo si lawlaw.”
(Even when things are not okay, we ensure safety first. We make use of whatever we can access to prevent danger).

This finding is comparable to the report by Garcia et al. (2021) which demonstrates miners' determination to use locally available materials such as remaining pieces of transparent plastic bags, shreds from clothes, or bandanas to prevent direct human-bare skin contact. This adaptability suggests that most miners strive to ensure their self-preservation despite their work dynamics. It suggests the need for support systems of all shapes to guarantee equitable access to sufficient safety gear.

“Nangina din chemical masks gamin, asi enggay kaman nasamay kami et, isunga no wada di facemask, mabalin et, di importante wada di proteksiyon ta adi diretso ay masungung din cyanide” - Ian (Chemical masks are expensive and we are already use to it, if there is facemask then it would be sufficient enough, as long as we have protection from directly inhaling the cyanide fumes).

Plate 14. Miner Using an Improvised Face Mask to Protect Against Cyanide Fume Inhalation

Miners reduce harm by managing wastewater generated during the CIP gold extraction process responsibly. Instead of letting runoffs with cyanide into the rivers, the miners have established an environmentally friendly process.

Plate 15. Treatment Pond for Cyanide-Laced CIP Water

Michael affirmed this:

“No man CIP kami, man-usar kami si kemikals kaman din cyanide, lime, carbon ya wada pay di udom. Din iman makin ammo tan wada di nangisuro ay nanpadpadas ay nabayag et man-amag da si kaman pangikulongan da sin danum ta asi da ibulos sin ginawang na malpas di kaat ay agew.” (If processing is done using CIP, cyanide and other chemicals are utilized. Individuals knowledgeable about cyanide effects have constructed a treatment pond and will delay water release for several days).

They use ponds and expose the water to sunlight, which promotes a photodecomposition reaction that degrades the cyanide compounds. Cyanide is decomposed, thus reducing its carryover risks and minimizing the contamination risks on freshwater ecosystems.

After proportionate degradation to manageable levels, it is then pushed out. The move is analogous to environmental research reports by scholars such as Garcia et al. (2019), in which they propose safe wastewater management as one of the most effective strategies for minimizing the ecological price in mining.

It is evident that while harm reduction strategies represent significant steps towards mitigating the negative impacts of mining, there remain challenges and opportunities for further improvement especially that miners are very dependent on chemicals. The miners' stories presented in this study showed an intense description of a complex web of economic pressures and systemic inequities that characterize small-

scale mining communities. Thus, despite being fully aware of the health and environmental implications that come with the use of chemicals such as mercury and dangerous substances, these miners are trapped in a cycle of economic dependence. In this case, they are forced to risk their health to earn a few coins that they need to put food on the table. Earl lamented:

“maga di maamagan mi, adi pay no adi kami man-usar si kemikal et natken high grade din mauto ay balitok, asi masayang din tailings tan siyat ud man-usar si kemikal tapno maala din nabaybay-an ay balitok, kasapulan mi abe di kumita ta wada mailako si kanen di pamilya” (We can't do anything, if we will not use chemicals then our gold will not be of high quality. There is a need also to use chemicals to retrieve gold from ore tailings, otherwise, the tailings will be just a waste).

In this study, the complex dynamics of miner's usage and dependency of mining chemicals is seen as a learning process for the miners themselves as they try to mitigate the harm. Technologies and innovations are wanted so as to reduce the harmful effects of these chemicals to the miners, their families, their communities and the environment.

Conclusions

Despite its importance to local economies, small-scale mining has historically posed significant environmental and health hazards due to the use of harmful chemicals. However, recent observations suggest a notable shift in chemical usage patterns in this sector, with the adoption of practices such as Carbon in Pulp (CIP) indicating an increasing awareness and proactive approach among small-scale miners to mitigate risks to human health and the environment. This shift, influenced in part by legal requirements, also demonstrates a genuine dedication to protecting vital ecosystems. The role of technological advancements and regulatory frameworks is crucial in driving these changes, offering a glimpse of a future where the use of harmful chemicals in small-scale mining could be eliminated. Nonetheless, challenges including resistance to change, limited access to information, and economic pressures persist. The following conclusions delve into the complex nature of these challenges.

1. It is clear that there is a significant shift in the patterns of chemical uses in small-scale mining as evidenced above. Adapting to the CIP process is a clear sign that small-scale miners are increasingly becoming proactive in promoting practices that are not risky to their health and that of the environment.

Such a change may also not be explained solely based on the pressure to comply with the laws but a willingness to ensure that the industry they depend on does not adversely impact the ecosystems on which they will also continue to depend. Nevertheless, the analysis of the chemical uses in mining processes explain the role

played by technology and the law in insulating the interested parties from the use of harmful chemicals in their operations.

With technology expected to continue playing a critical role in the evolution of the sector, it is possible that matters such as harmful chemical use will continue to form part of history in small-scale mining. Although the future looks good in small-scale mining, the full achieving of the removal all harmful chemicals remains a challenge due to resistance, poor access to information, and greed.

2. The perceived effects on health and the environment in small – scale mining areas present a grim picture of the situation faced by the miners and surrounding populations. While the former risk their lives in dangerous settings due to chemical exposure, the latter face long-term environmental degradation due to the same. These issues are a considerable threat to human well-being and ecosystem integrity and require immediate and long-term consideration for solutions. The situation can only improve through a multi-faceted approach integrating immediate and long-term responses towards sustainable development.

In the short term, health effects should be addressed through enhanced safety during duties, access to health services, and appropriate information on the handling of chemicals.

Simultaneously, pollution and environmental degradation call for immediate action to avoid irreparable damage to health and livelihoods. The process should uphold equity, justice, and human rights to avoid disproportionately burdening the most vulnerable populations.

3. Miners' experiences offer critical insights into the complex realities of small-scale mining community residents. They paint a vivid picture of the extent of the challenges they face, ranging from the health challenges derived from exposure to various chemicals to the environmental degradation of their habitats resulting from mining activities.

Additionally, they offer a sober reminder of the urgent need to address the myriad issues affecting residents of mining communities. Indeed, the challenges presented call for holistic solutions that address the miners' well-being and the sustenance of their environments.

4. Successful remedies will require listening to the miners' voices and ensuring their active participation in the formulation of possible interventions to

their challenges. This may include efforts to improve access to medical services, provide safe working conditions, and explore alternative sources of livelihood to reduce the over-reliance on mining. Further, miners' firsthand experience emphasizes the critical role that the environment plays in their lives, promoting a more holistic view of development that recognizes the interconnectedness of human and ecosystems health. Addressing

the underlying causes of health and environmental problems will be important in developing long-lasting solutions that benefit the current and succeeding generations.

5. It is obvious that the harm-reduction strategies are essential to protect miners' well-being and decrease the environmental impact of small-scale mining. The narratives of the miners demonstrate their perseverance and innovation in addressing both safety and environmental issues under constrained circumstances. In the future, however, we can do more to enhance these efforts with integrated approaches that address risks' contributing factors in mining communities. This includes more education and training on safety procedures, responsible waste management, and developing alternative sources of income to eliminate dependency on dangerous mining.

Recommendations

Evolving Patterns of Chemical Usage to Address the Evolving Pattern of Chemical Usage in Mining, it is essential for various stakeholders to work together. Miners must be required to have more access to personal protective equipment, need to be better informed through information-sharing platforms, and should be assumed to understand the regulations and take responsibility for their conduct.

Local Government Units have an important role in terms of monitoring the impacts on health and the environment of the chemical pattern associated to promote successful remediation of mining-related impacts on geographical areas, as well as in community-based initiatives aimed at alleviating the impacts of chemical usage on mining.

At the national level, harsh enforcement of laws concerning chemical usage, the phasing out of unsafe chemicals, the reward of incentives to entice safe modes of mining, and the allocation of further financing of complementary study into sustainable solutions are essential. The specific recommendations are as follows:

1. Access and Education: Miners must be required to have more access to personal protective equipment. Additionally, miners need to be better informed through information-sharing platforms and should be assumed to understand the regulations and take responsibility for their conduct.

2. Local Government and National Actions: Local Government Units should monitor the impacts on health and the environment of the evolving chemical usage patterns, promote successful remediation of mining-related impacts, and initiate community-based initiatives. At the national level, there should be harsh enforcement of laws concerning chemical usage, the phasing out of unsafe chemicals, provision of incentives for safe mining practices, and allocation of funding for sustainable solution studies.

Perceived Effects on Health and Environment Concerning the perceived impact

on the health of local populations and the environment, the miners are expected to mobilize active health education campaigns and adhere to strict safety professional standards. LGUs, responsible for monitoring and surveillance, should step up monitoring activities, institute quick remedial measures, and provide support to community-based programs addressing the health and environmental concerns in the mining-impacted areas.

The national government should, in turn, concentrate on tougher mining regulation, broad-based health promotion programs, and potential diversified levels of health care to the affected communities. The specific recommendations are as follows:

3. Health and Safety Campaigns: Miners should mobilize active health education campaigns and adhere to strict safety professional standards. Local Government Units should step up monitoring activities, institute quick remedial measures, and support community-based programs addressing health and environmental concerns.

4. Government Actions and Community Participation: The national government should focus on tougher mining regulations, health promotion programs, and diversified healthcare for affected communities. Strengthening monitoring and surveillance systems, implementing remedial actions on existing hazards, disseminating health information, and ensuring community participation with adequate funding and support are essential steps.

Harm Reduction Strategies Miners should be helped with the access to personal protective equipment and should be trained. Well-thought environmental management plans should be developed by Local Government Units, and relief options should be introduced to local communities.

On the national level, the government should fund safety training courses and establish policies where the environment is considered no less important than mining itself.

In whole, the efforts of all involved stakeholders should be united to ensure sustainable and non-hazardous mining focused on people and the environment. The specific recommendations are as follows:

5. Access to PPE and Training: Ensuring regular access to personal protective equipment through earmarked funds, financial incentives, and free training for proper use is crucial. Expanding safety training and education programs with customized modules and additional support is also necessary.

6. Environmental Management and Sustainable Practices: Developing and enacting environmental management plans focusing on waste reduction, pollution prevention, land restoration, and ecosystem conservation should be prioritized.

Promoting sustainable practices and alternative livelihoods for mining, convening

multi-stakeholder groups, and facilitating forums to exchange best practices and share resources are necessary for effective harm reduction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that this study adhered to the highest ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the research, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. Participants were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. The confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were rigorously maintained throughout the research process, safeguarding their personal information and responses. The well-being of participants was prioritized, with measures in place to ensure their safety and comfort during the study. There is no conflict of interest associated with the conduct of this research, and all findings were interpreted impartially and objectively. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were properly cited. The results of this study are presented purely for research purposes, contributing to the broader understanding of the topic without any personal or financial bias.

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